

A survey of meta maintenance

Dear Participant,

You have been specially invited to participate in the research project described below.

PROJECT TITLE: Evaluating Meta Maintenance in Open Source Software Development

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* Required

What is the project about?

The aim of this project is to evaluate our proposed new approach of contributions to FLOSS projects. Because of the reusability of FLOSS, pieces of source code from the same origins spread to multiple software repositories are maintained independently, which can cause the obsolescence of source code and the increasing risk of defects and vulnerabilities. For these issues, we intend to aggregate various changes for source code of the same origins, compose integrated changes, and distribute to FLOSS projects that have the related source code. We call this approach meta maintenance. We hope to be able to have a better grasp in understanding important points of such contributions so that we can build practical tools of meta maintenance.

Why am I invited?

The criteria is a contributor over the age of 18 with contributions to a chosen sample of GitHub software projects. Your varying experience should provide a range of responses.

What is asked of me?

A simple survey with questions for external contributions to a selected project. These questions will be in the form of short answers or multiple choice. All questions are worded to be as comprehensive as possible and do not require any complicated thought processes.

How long is the survey?

The survey should take roughly 5-10 minutes.

What risks are associated with participation?

No foreseeable risks are associated with participating in this project.

Can I withdraw from the project?

Participation in this project is completely voluntary. If you agree to participate, you can withdraw from the study at any time. The survey is short and requires little contribution, therefore withdrawal is as easy as closing the survey web page. You can also request deleting your answers by sending us your participation ID with the form.

https://drive.google.com/open?id=1_tiM94vP_ENXp2jTaKm7YWosPzZOjeQI

What will happen to my information?

The information will be used to answer research questions and will be produced in a final paper, but no information will lead to any possible privacy breach or identification of participants. The results of the study may be used for a future extension project. All information will be stored on password-encrypted servers at Nara Institute of Science and Technology.

Who do I contact if I have questions about the project?

Dr. Hideaki Hata (hata@is.naist.jp), Nara Institute of Science and Technology,

Dr. Christoph Treude (christoph.treude@adelaide.edu.au), University of Adelaide,

Dr. Raula Gaikovina Kula (raula-k@is.naist.jp), Nara Institute of Science and Technology,

Dr. Takashi Ishio (ishio@is.naist.jp), Nara Institute of Science and Technology.

1. If I want to participate, what do I do? *

Please agree to the consent form (https://drive.google.com/open?id=1MyA_bLQmWGps0mPozj-S3o_GOAlpMHpl) and proceed to fill in survey. Once completed, press submit to complete the survey.

Mark only one oval.

I consent and therefore agree to take part in this research project.

Questions on Meta Maintenance

2. Participation ID (only for deleting your answers on your request)

3. How would you best describe yourself? *

Mark only one oval.

Core developer of this project

Casual contributor

Other: _____

4. How experienced are you with this project? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Very inexperienced	<input type="radio"/>	Very experienced				

Regarding this file in your project,
<https://github.com/PROJ1/PATH/TO/FILE>

We have found that another repository is maintaining the same file and applied different changes:
<https://github.com/PROJ2/PATH/TO/FILE>

We are wondering whether it would make sense to notify you of these changes from another repository, with the goal to potentially apply them in your project.

5. Is maintaining this file important? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Low Priority (not a significant file)	<input type="radio"/>	High Priority (Important file)				

6. Which of the following maintenance activities interests you regard to this file?

Check all that apply.

- Corrective maintenance (e.g., bug fixing)
- Adaptive maintenance (e.g., mirroring, third-party library update, license change, documentation)
- Perfective maintenance (e.g., new features, performance improvement, refactoring)
- Preventive maintenance (e.g., testing, reviewing, software analytics)

Other: _____

7. Are these specific modifications to the same file in another repository relevant to your project? Why/Why not?

8. In general, are you interested in modifications that have been applied to files in other repositories that your repository also contains? *

Mark only one oval.

	1	2	3	4	5	
Has little interest	<input type="radio"/>	Has large interest				

9. What makes these changes in another repository interesting or not interesting for your project?

10. What kind of changes to files that your repository also contains would you be interested in?

11. Any comments?

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